

Training in Psychology in Brazil – Reflections on the Role of Early Supervised Internships in Undergraduate Courses

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Abstract—This paper presents observations on the early supervised internships in Psychology, currently called *basic internships* in Brazil, and its importance in professional training. The work is an experience report and focuses on the Professional training, illustrated by the reality of a Brazilian institution, used as a case study. It was developed from the authors' experience as academic supervisors of this kind of practice throughout this undergraduate course, combined with aspects investigated in the post-doctoral research of one of them. Theoretical references on the subject and related national legislation are analyzed, as well as reports of students who experienced at least one semester of this type of practice, articulated to the observations of the authors. The results demonstrate the importance of the early supervised internships as a way of creating opportunities for the students of a first contact with the professional reality and the practice of psychologists in different fields of insertion, preparing them for further experiments that require more involvement in activities of training and practices in Psychology.

Keywords—Training of psychologists, Internships in Psychology, Supervised internships, Combination of theory and practice.

I. INTRODUCTION

PSYCHOLOGY is a field of knowledge and professional practice whose undergraduate courses has proliferated in recent decades in Brazil. It is possible to observe significant changes since the reality of the late 80's. If in that time undergraduate courses in Psychology were offered at a few universities and organized with disciplines distributed at different shifts of the day, currently it is conducted in higher education institutions of different sizes, often with disciplines concentrated on only one shift.

The option to offer the course at nighttime facilitated the entry of the working students, which combines their professional training with some labor activity exerted during the day or part thereof, in most cases, are not directly linked with the field of Psychology.

The observed changes in Psychology's undergraduate courses and their characteristics, on the one hand, expanded

the search for this profession and made it viable for people who previously perceived it as elitist and inaccessible. On the other hand, generated the challenge of maintaining quality of undergraduate programs and, once established essential criteria for this, combine the characteristics of the course with the demands of training. Ensuring that it is able to train qualified professionals, it enabled a practice in an ethical and qualified manner. Reference [1] discusses the importance of taking into account, to outline the training in Psychology, aspects such as the social context in which the professional exercises its activities, its responsibilities in this context and the characteristics of the higher education institution which has the role of educating him/her.

Many professionals have been working to solve the challenges of training in contexts with different specificities, with the task of outlining the curricula of these courses.

In colleges where curricular activities occur mainly during the night, a concern, among others, has been to enable the realization of the internships and practices for the working students, who develop labor activities during part of the day or in the whole of it, preparing these apprentices for their future practice in various contexts of the Brazilian labor market.

This paper describes the experience conducted in an undergraduate degree program in Psychology, in which the authors are professors, members of groups charged with the task of designing and reviewing the pedagogical project of the course and internship's supervisors. The work was developed with considerations on these issues and focusing especially on the importance of the early supervised internships (currently called, in Brazil, in accordance with current legislation, *basic internships*), as an approximation of the student with the professional reality and practice of the psychologists in the context of the Brazilian labor market.

II. BRAZILIAN LEGISLATION RELATED TO TRAINING IN PSYCHOLOGY

Psychology in Brazil, until the middle of last century, was practiced by professionals who did their training in other countries or postgraduate courses. These professionals brought to the country contributions of different theories and practices and established their practices restricted primarily to operations in Rio de Janeiro - São Paulo axis [2]. Initially, as a field of knowledge, Psychology was introduced on the national scene primarily by physicians who, as noted [3], developed relevant reflections on themes related to it in their final papers for undergraduates. According to this author,

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Psychology also gained ground in Brazil, through the work of teachers in the basic levels of education, who articulated the area to work with children and their relation to learning.

The recognition of Psychology as a profession came only in 1962 [4], establishing the training in this area initially inserted in the faculties of Philosophy. The first Psychology undergraduate course in Brazil, however, had already been created in 1953, at the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-RJ) [5]. According to the pedagogical models prevalent at that time, with regard to higher education, the undergraduate Psychology's course was delivered in early disciplines, considered basic and professional disciplines, which the students should attend later, towards the end of their training.

In this sense, the basic disciplines integrated initial curricula of different undergraduate courses in related areas, while the disciplines understood in the perspective of professional content, indispensable to the practice in a specific area, were different for each particular undergraduate course.

After the theoretical training, students were enabled to enter institutions where they could develop practical activities, all supervised by a professional with experience. In line with the flexnerian model deployed from American references in various courses in the area of health care [6], although then considered in most universities as a course in the humanities, the curricula of the first Brazilian undergraduate courses in Psychology had strong division between theory and practice, each experienced at different times of training, which resulted, for the student, in a difficulty of integrating the practice with theories that sustained it.

This initial training model, although it can still be seen in varying degrees in some currently existing undergraduate courses, passed over the years to suffer criticism. As pointed out by [7], the distinction between disciplines that compose the basic core, the vocational core and the professional practices, generates a fragmentation between theoretical knowledge and professional knowledge and leads the students to the difficulty in establishing connections between their practical experience and theory that supposedly underpins it, without building this joint progressively. It is a model that has its roots in the disciplinary fragmentation and dissociation between practice and theory that characterizes the Cartesian paradigm and, as noted by [8], creates in health care major difficulties in professional activities and consequently problems for the subjects who need it, since the patient is not perceived in its entirety.

In this sense, it is important to remember, when it comes to Psychology, the artificiality that is present in a so segmented professional training, if we think, as stresses [9], that authors in this area, such as Freud, Jung and Rogers, also did not perform segmentations between theory and professional practice, because it was just from the reflection on the care of patients that the theory was conceived and formulated by each one. That is, it is natural to integrate clinical practice to theoretical training, in a constant process of reflection between theory and practice.

The pedagogical model that proposed the segmentation

between theory and practice, therefore, as well as the deficiencies that were generated in the training observed with its implementation, received harsh criticism, leading to a process of reformatting curricula and searching for alternatives to building courses capable of enabling future professionals with the ability to link theory and practice, as soon as possible, at their undergraduate courses.

In the case of Brazil, the internship programs have their guidelines proposed, in first place, by the Ministry of Labour and Employment, which, in Law 11.788 [10] establishes the principles that guide this type of learning and the integration of the student into services of different natures. In this context, the internship program is set, in the first article of the law, as *supervised school education act, developed in the workplace, aiming for the preparation of productive work of students who are attending regular schools, higher education institutions, vocational education, secondary education, special education, final years of primary education, vocational mode of youth and adult education.*

The legislation points the internships as relevant to professional training and classifies it as *mandatory*, when it is included in the course curriculum, and *not mandatory*, when its realization is a student's option in order to enhance their training. In the case of practices related to higher education, the legislation also establishes mandatory monitoring by a supervisor in internship field and a supervisor professor of the educational institution. The legislation also limits the performance of the trainee at the institution to which he belongs to a maximum of 6 hours per day and the duration of the practice for a period not exceeding two years.

Institutions of higher education, when developing curricula and organizing other parameters regarding the operation of its undergraduate courses, also take into account other documents such as the recommendations established by the Law of Guidelines and Bases of Education (LDB – 9.394), approved in 1996 [11]. This law aims, among other things, for the need to establish minimum guidelines for undergraduate courses, which should serve as a guide for the development of curricula of each training area. The first version of the document for Psychology courses, the *National Curriculum Guidelines for Training in Psychology* was established in 2004 [12], using as a guide the goal of forming a professional who had *skills* and *abilities* such as health care, making decisions, communicating, leading, administering and managing, in addition to adopting the goal of continuing education.

The teaching in this perspective should be covered by *structural axes*, training for the exercise of practice in Psychology and building skills related to research and teaching capacity in the area.

Taking into account the plurality of theoretical perspectives that pervade psychology and opportunities to operate in different areas, the document also states that the curricula of the courses should offer collections of disciplines that characterize *curricular emphasis*. These emphases, characterized by skills and abilities built by concentration studies and internships focused on training aimed at the professional expertise in specific areas, could facilitate a

generalist education to the future psychologist, but focused more directly to the performance in specific areas.

Among the emphases mentioned as possibilities, and not closing the possibility of the development of others, the document cited *Psychology and processes of scientific research; Psychology and educational processes; Psychology and management processes; Psychology and processes for prevention and health promotion; Psychology and clinical processes and Procedures for diagnostic evaluation*. The document also proposed that the disciplines composing the curriculum were grouped, therefore, into two groups: the *common core*, with appropriate contents for general education and the *core of competencies*, focused on training in the emphasis proposed by each higher education institution.

According to [13], a relevant concept brought in by the National Curriculum Guidelines 2004 aspect - DCN 2004, was the inclusion of Psychology between the professions in the health care area, aspect in line with the decision of the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Health of thinking together on the training of skilled professionals to work in the Unified Health System - SUS, public system whose assignment is to offer the Brazilian population health care.

With regard to the internships, the DCN 2004 proposes an amendment in relation to what was then prevailing in the country. Aiming to present a proposed solution to the problems caused by fragmentation between theory and practice in the training, which was previously illustrated by the concentration of disciplines in the first year of undergraduate courses and internships at its end, the document proposed the inclusion of practices already in the early stages of undergraduation. In this sense, the document divided performing practices by students into *basic supervised internships* and *specific supervised internships*.

The basic internship should enable the student to develop activities related to the competencies and skills provided in the common core disciplines in the curriculum. On the other hand, the specific internship aimed to enable students to experience the insertion in different institutions and perform practices related to the specific design of each institution, also considering the emphasis laid on curriculum practices. Together, basic supervised internships and specific supervised internships in undergraduate Psychology courses, should make up 15% of their total workload, which according to Resolution No. 2, 2007 of the Camera of Higher Education of the Ministry of Education [14], should make up between 3600 and 4000 hours for bachelor degree programs, as considered the training in Psychology in Brazil, and time required to complete the course of minimum 5 years.

Another important aspect of the 2004 version of the DCN was pointing out the need to create in each institution of higher education, psychological services related to the desired competencies for professionals coming from the course. In undergraduate courses with an emphasis on clinical processes, for example, this determination has been consolidated in the creation of *University-clinics*, in which students can conduct clinical activities supervised by professionals usually linked to the institution of higher education with experience in the area.

The relevance of this contribution of the DCN in 2004 is highlighted by [15], when he discusses the importance of University-clinics for the training of students of Psychology's undergraduate courses, since when joining these services, students can put into practice what they learn in theoretical disciplines.

In 2011, a new version of the National Curriculum Guidelines for Training in Psychology in Brazil (DCN 2011) [16] was published, still in effect in the country.

This document retained most of the propositions presented in 2004, including, however, guidelines for the inclusion of teacher training in the area of Psychology in the pedagogical design of the courses, characterized as Licensure in Psychology. It can be taken by students throughout the training in Psychology or after its completion.

It is important to note that the licensure in Psychology, as mentioned by [17] had been envisaged at the time of regularization of the profession in 1962 and was offered in some institutions of higher education since then, but not with the obligation highlighted in DCN 2011. In this sense, this legislation established the need to include in the design of the undergraduate courses in Psychology, the knowledge and skills related to the student's training for teaching, as well as the minimum workload of 500 hours in disciplines and 300 hours of supervised practice. The document thus created the need for the inclusion of projects of licensure articulated in Brazilian Psychology courses, something that, until today, has not been implemented in most of the higher education institutions.

It should be noted that this measure had the backdrop of a movement for inclusion of Psychology as a discipline of high school and the consequent need to train professionals for its exercise. However, this inclusion did not happen yet and maintaining the mandatory offering disciplines related to the licensure is under discussion, because as mentioned [18], despite the expanding field of work for psychologist's teachers, training should be rethought, providing larger subsidies to overcome the peculiarities that this activity requires. The authors also point out that, if it is offered, training for teaching in Psychology should happen throughout the course, without the need for supplementary hours after the same, ending the segmentation between the bachelor, the psychologist and the licensed in Psychology.

Regarding legislation establishing principles for the development and operation of graduate programs in Psychology in Brazil, it is also important to emphasize the considerations of the Federal Council of Psychology (CFP), included therein resolutions contained in the Ethical Code for Psychology Professionals [19], whose principles should be presented to students and considered among the desired skills for professionals who completed the course. The Federal Council of Psychology (CFP) has recently published, in 2013, another important document for the preparation of projects for the internships of undergraduate courses, the *Charter of services on internships and training institutions* [20], understanding that the internship is an initial step of the profession and link with training and practice in Psychology.

Thus, the performance of the trainee and the responsibility for developing standards for the realization of the internships, while articulation between vocational training and exercise, fit both the educational institution and the regulatory institution of professional practice. The document summarizes the notes of others discussed earlier in this paper, and also establishes certain procedures regarding the orientation of trainees in the fields of student's practice and actions to be undertaken by the training institution.

One point that is in question, considering what is proposed in this paper, is the possibility of the student to conduct the required internships, established as prerequisites for training in Psychology and part of the organization of curricula, as previously mentioned, without supervision by a psychologist in the training field.

This lack of mandatory local supervision is the effect of the shortage of professionals in certain regions of the country and the consequent difficulty of establishing training fields. This relaxation of the rules, in the opinion of the authors, can cause a depletion of training and even offer risk to the quality of the internship experience and risk to patients or users involved. This point has often been discussed in different forums for professionals and questioned by some segments and groups.

III. THE REALITY OF THE FOCUSED INSTITUTION

In this paper the case of a higher education institution will be studied, in which the undergraduate degree course in Psychology is currently starting in the 7th semester. The authors are, since its implementation, alternately, coordinators of basic supervised internships 1, 2 and 3. So far, two groups of basic internship 1 (total of 20 students), and one group of basic internship 2 (with 10 students) were finalized. This second group is, during the second half of 2014, in the basic internship 3, and a new group of 20 students is performing the basic internship 1. Until December 2014, therefore, the institution will have accompanied one group of basic internship 3, two groups of basic internship 2 and three groups of basic internship 3. The specific supervised internships begin in 2015, with an emphasis in *Psychology and clinical processes*, lasting two semesters. In March 2016 graduates of that current year may attend an internship in the emphasis of *Psychology and management processes* (characterized by the work related to Psychology of organizations or institutional practice) and in the second half of the year, they will hold the last specific internship, in an area of free choice.

In the basic internship 1, students experience practices in two or at most three institutions (schools, clinics, companies, etc.), in order to observe the work of professionals in different areas, described by the Regional Council of Psychology (CRP) [21], without the possibility to conduct interventions.

Students observe and record their impressions to later conduct a report, which must necessarily articulate theory with practice, describing the entire period of internship, as well as developing a critical analysis, which should contain their impressions when knowing the professional practice of psychologists. The students must also conduct interviews with the psychologist who supervises the practice in the training

field, establishing reflections on their professional area and how to conduct practices. In the basic internship 2, the observation is held in more hours, preferably in a single institution, with exchange of service permitted, if the student experiences any hindrance to the process or development of the activity. Students record their observations and can develop their first intervention if it is performed with the accompaniment of the field supervisor. The report is also requested, in the same manner as the previous one, with linkage of theory and practice through critical analysis, as well as the interview with the professional supervisor.

The basic internship 3 follows the same model as the basic internship 2. The difference is the number of hours that the trainees remain in the institution and also the intervention that they perform, which although limited to a few specific practices, can already happen without the presence of the local supervisor, but should, however, be planned in conjunction with this professional. Students are also instructed to perform a more elaborate report than the previous one, since the observation time is extended and the articulation of theory and practice can be deepened.

It is up to the students to seek to know the theory behind the practice of the internship institution and complement their training, if necessary, considering the theoretical plurality composing Psychology as a science and profession. The academic supervisor assists in the preparation and discussion of the report, through supervision meetings, collective and individual, in which the analysis of professional practice is always on the agenda. Students are encouraged to report their experiences with the backdrop of ethics that should underpin all the work.

It is important to note the significance of the moments of socialization, in which students are encouraged to report their observations to colleagues, exchanging experiences with these, in the meetings of collective supervision. Even though these experiences may be perceived as common, these make up the professional universe, which must be discovered by each student, so he/she can start to build a practice through the personal experience of observing the performance of a more experienced colleague.

The students therefore begin to compose a unique repertoire, the way of being psychologists, from their own experiences underpinned by an understanding of the reality of each institution in which they are placed.

IV. METHOD

In order to investigate the relevance of practices afforded by the early supervised internships, improve the way to conduct their guidance and, if necessary, make changes regarding the setting of the proposal, the authors developed a short questionnaire, aimed at students who had already completed at least one semester of practice. Students were asked to answer the following questions:

1. What internships have you performed or are you now performing in Psychology undergraduate degree course?
2. What do you think you learned in basic supervised internships until the present time?

3. In your opinion, which is the role played by the field supervisor and the academic supervisor in guiding the trainee?
4. What differences do you suppose there are among the basic internships and specific internships in professional training?
5. What is the theoretical line used by your field supervisor?
6. What is the influence of the theoretical perspective of your field supervisor in your training as a psychologist?

The answers to some of these questions were articulated to the observations of the authors and theoretical references on the topics covered, as well as comments from individuals who participated in the post-doctoral research of one of the authors¹. These elements served also as a point of starting for discussions brought to this work.

In this sense, this work is characterized, as pointed out by [22] as a case study. As proposed by this author, the paper, therefore, begins with a topic to be studied, i.e., the effects of the inclusion of initial practices in Psychology undergraduate degree courses, the *basic supervised internships*, with further study of a specific case, here made possible by the practice of the authors in one particular higher education institution, with theorizing about the case investigated.

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the progressive implementation of the three basic supervised internships in this higher educational institution, the proposed inclusion of students in the fields of practice was being evaluated and some necessary changes have been made to qualify their training and thus the first experiences of articulation between theory and practice offered to them. In this time of training, they relate practices, theories and techniques studied in the course, experience made possible by the introduction of students in the training field, which has proved essential to their training. As one student said, when answering question 2 of the questionnaire, the internship in an institution with children, for example, *enabled her to relate practice and theory on Human Development*. At the same time, many issues that have arisen over the implementation of the basic internships generated the need for faculty reflections and changes to qualify the proposal.

The difficulties that initially emerged in the basic internship 1 at the time of its implementation, was related with the initial time of permanence of the trainees in each institution, considered too short by the teams who welcomed them and their requests for inclusion in services. In this sense, the expected time of only two or three shifts of observation in each institution was perceived as insufficient for the proposed work for the psychologist of the institution was known by the student.

Thus, the observation time for each service was expanded, with the removal of one institution, to keep the insertion time originally planned, totaling 32 hours, distributed in two services. Thus, the demand of institutions, which often refused

to receive a student for observation for short periods, since this also mobilized a team as well as the individuals involved, especially in cases where children were present, such as in preschools and traditional clinical care.

Regarding supervisory practices, academic supervisors have privileged the collective space for discussion. The orientation and the consequent collective reflection can assist in questioning the practice.

Initially, when there was a proposal to the students that the orientation meetings of basic supervised internships 1 and 2 happen together, some expressed their discontent, claiming that bringing together two groups at different times of the course was not productive. However, this discontent vanished from the exchanges that have occurred since the first meetings and personal enrichment from the account of the experience of colleagues, even those most beginners.

Currently, the trainees of the basic internship 1 have their collective orientations conducted in part along with the students of basic internships 2 and 3 and, in part, separately, in order to ensure a space for bureaucratic guidelines demanded at the beginning of practices, such as instructions for the preparation of reports and interviews.

At the same time, the collective supervision of basic internship 2 and 3 happen together, promoting dialogue between all participants. The identification of students with some institutions and practices began to be envisioned, especially regarding the area of Social Psychology, in which work with communities and individuals in psychological distress seems to mobilize the trainees more intensely. Students, after completion of the probationary period, often end up engaging in other extra-curricular activities in the services, in which they were inserted, as a way to continue exercising a practice that mobilized and sparked interest in higher engagement.

The work of academic supervisor, in some cases, was initially focused on dialogue with the institutions in which trainees were inserted, seeking to clarify the doubts that arose, preparing work plans and combinations between the college and the services involved.

In parallel, the supervisors sought to meet the demand for solving the difficulties that arose, especially with students' questions about the work done by the psychologist of the internship field. In many instances, there were, by the students, for example, several questions about the procedures and practices adopted by the supervisor of this professional. Among these issues, doubts about the coherence of professional practice observed and theoretical line that this psychologist said adopting appeared frequently.

The existing tension often was one more ingredient to improve the quality of the discussions that occurred in collective meetings, which sought, among other things, to clarify points on which students reflected, trying to understand the practice of psychologists. Students could, from a critical analysis made possible by group discussions, broaden the understanding of the reality presented, as well as reflect on the practice of psychologists in different contexts.

¹ Work performed in the Graduate Program in Education – PPGEDU - UFRGS, under the supervision of Dr. Maria Folberg.

In this sense, the experience of early internships has been showing also an important way to provide the student with knowledge about different styles of professional experience, diversifying models offered by contact with college professors. One of the students who responded the questionnaire, for example, says, answering the question 2 of this instrument, that he learned *a lot about how a professional should behave facing unexpected situations that happen in everyday life*. The student says, too, that the realization of the basic internships has proved essential in *understanding issues related to ethics, essential for the realization of the work with humans*. This student also adds that the experience of realization of the basic internships has proven essential to the understanding professional intervention from the Psychoanalytic theory, whose study he focuses and in which he has a special interest, when he says: *I think that so far all supervisors with whom I did internships have had great influence on my career and training, since all of them work with Psychoanalysis and this is the theoretical line that I intend to follow*.

The perception of the possibility of psychologist working in different areas and contexts is one of the important aspects that the completion of basic internship has enabled. The experience allows students to broaden interest often initially very focused in the clinical area, knowing other perspectives for future professional activities. As pointed out by [23], it is from this reflection on the practice of the psychologist, that professionals in Brazil began to enter into proposals of diversified services, as stations of public health and works with poor communities, for example, attending a demand not previously thought of as possible for the exercise of psychology as a profession. This is illustrated in the speech of a student of Psychology, interviewed during the postdoctoral research of one of the authors, when she says that *when she joined the course she thought a lot about acting in the clinical area, but with time and the internships in other areas it changed*.

At the same time, conducting brief remarks on professional practice provides students with the opportunity to get to know, at least superficially, certain aspects of practice areas or work with specific audiences for which they do not intend to opt in their careers, but would like to know. One of the students who responded to the questionnaire, for example, mentioned, in response to question 1, that *the experience was rewarding because it allowed him to know the practice of a school psychologist, inserted in an institution of early childhood education*. Although the student has no desire to act in this area or work with children, he affirmed that knowing a little about this possibility *was essential* to his training.

On the other hand, also for students who perform their training in institutions that propose ways to intervene in the clinical area, the experience proves exciting and provides reflections on various aspects. In this sense, the doubts about the characterization of certain ways of intervention such as clinical practice, for example, have generated important discussions in the group, allowing an extension of the conception of this area. The possibility of observing a clinical

practice in different contexts from those that characterize a traditional setting, which can be characterized as extended clinic [24], certainly proven crucial for the professional who will act in different segments of the Brazilian labor market, and especially in public care services.

This is reinforced by [25], who points out that the training of psychologists able to act taking into consideration the design of extended clinic is key to tackling the Unified Health System - SUS and thus meet the Brazilian population that seeks care in public services. Thus, the traditional clinic, which as stresses [26] is often idealized by students as the most interesting area of expertise, when joining an undergraduate course in Psychology, begins to be reviewed and a change and consequent construction of a new perspective at the practice of the psychologist can be seen.

In this sense, the training in clinical Psychology, as is proposed in the pedagogical project of the institution examined in this work as one of its emphases, is now perceived more by listening and intervention position on the reality in which the student is inserted, than by acting in one type of service or specific setting.

At the same time, in the collective and individual supervisions, students and supervisors discuss aspects concerning the ethical stance that should be adopted in the face of realities observed. Thus, the interpretation of reality and the intervention in the institutions in which students take contact with this should be understood by those from a theoretical understanding and reflection on this reality, replacing the emotive reading, constructed solely from the subjectivity of them and their personal history.

An example of these aspects can be seen in the comments of students placed in contexts such as residential care institutions. If initially the trainees talk about the fact that they *would like to adopt children*, for example, over time they were able to establish new ways of integration with the institution and seek for theoretical and technical contributions on proposals of intervention in the context studied. Thus, they developed workshops on various projects to be undertaken with the sheltered children. The reinterpretation of social reality in which students are included, as well as the experience to intervene with the services in which this reality is present, allows trainees to broaden their view on the practice of psychologists in different contexts, making them more capable of working in Brazilian health and care services.

Some realities observed mobilized personal feelings of the trainees, often leading them to think about the possibility of seeking psychotherapy or personal analysis. This is a point often emphasized by supervisors, but that cannot be required by the institution of higher education, as previously discussed by [27]. With this, students often begin psychotherapy prior to beginning the specific supervised internship in clinical Psychology, in which the intervention of the student is inherent in the proposal. Thus, these students may prove more able to deal with their personal issues, a key to the training of a psychologist.

Psychoanalysis is one of the main theoretical lines studied at the institution that was focused in this work. Thus, it is

critical that students can consider, in their training, the famous tripod proposed by [28], when he mentions the importance of supporting the training and, consequently, clinical practice, in theoretical study, supervision with more experienced colleagues and personal analysis. Therefore, if on one hand the personal analysis or psychotherapy cannot be placed between the requirements proposed by the curriculum of the course, it has proven crucial in the training of the student of Psychology in an undergraduate course with one of the emphases in clinical processes.

In this sense, it should be added that knowing the theoretical line of greatest interest, through a personal experience of analysis or therapy, may also be an important way to choose, more safely, paths that go in search of theoretical frameworks that will underpin their future practice. It should be added that the experience of personal analysis, as well as the practice enabled by the internships, also allow the student to experience in their interventions the contents studied throughout the disciplines. This aspect becomes especially relevant with regard to the learning of listening, an essential element in a course that has Psychoanalysis in a privileged theoretical line in training and one of the emphases in *clinical processes*. It is demonstrated by a student interviewed for the post doctoral research of one of the authors, previously mentioned, when she comments: *I learn a lot in my personal analysis. About how to listen ... Funny, talking about listening to someone who is listening to you. But I learn a lot in my analysis!*

The experience provided by internships and contact with contents that will base a professional practice provided by those, along with the personal analysis or therapy may, therefore, constitute an initial step towards building a professional performance that takes into account the tripod proposed by Freud. The early supervised internships are crucial elements in this respect, since they are moments in which the student can experience the importance of these aspects of training and at the same time, build an acting style from observing more experienced colleagues. As one student says, in response to question 6, performing basic internships allowed him to *observe the psychologist acting and, knowing about his theory, to articulate what he has learned and check its effects in the practice.*

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Although still fairly recent in Brazil, the introduction of early supervised internships in the training of psychologists, considering the experience of the higher educational institution focused in this work and its introduction of practices in previous moments of the undergraduate course have been considered very positive, if compared to the previous curricular models of 2004.

The basic internships appear to contribute to the preparation of students for specific internships. As one student said in the questionnaire, in response to question 5, the first one concerns *the observation of the work of the psychologist and the specific internship refers directly to the interventions. It is*

when the student gets to choose the area in which he wishes to work in after graduating.

On the one hand, as some students mentioned in the questionnaire responses, the experience provided by the basic internships enables articulation of theoretical aspects covered in the course with professional practices established from theoretical lines and different contexts. On the other hand, these internships provide, in contact with the field supervisor, the building of identification models, established with a critical gaze, enabled by group discussions and individual supervisions with the academic supervisor.

The comments of the students, while being supervised, lead to the conclusion that basic supervised internships can be configured as an important way to know not only different work contexts, but different socio-economic realities, which at first can mobilize intense feelings in the intern. Dealing with these feelings and building forms of intervention with these realities and their audiences, thus shows an essential aspect to training. In this sense, this type of training can also be important as a way of preparing the students for the practice that they will perform in specific internships and after the completion of the course, since these realities, then, no longer show in the scary optical it had in a first impact.

We know that Psychology is an area that demands professionals that work in it the possibility of a critical position towards realities in which they live, in its many facets and possible configurations. From the observation of a more experienced colleague and progressive integration in practical activities, the basic internship allows the students to learn a little more about the universe that characterizes the profession, supported by the theoretical framework that they have been studying at the undergraduate level and discussions about their experience in services in which it appears.

In this sense, the case study presented in this paper seems to indicate that changes in legislation made possible by DCN 2004 are positive for the training of psychologists in Brazil, allowing the capacitation of a professional who comes to the labor market with more diverse experiences, established along the undergraduate degree, and greater contact with the different contexts of professional practice and social realities of the country.

Thus, possibly creating early internships in Brazilian undergraduate courses in Psychology can contribute to the training of self-assured professionals when they begin their professional practice and who are more able to hold a consistent performance with the Brazilian social reality and different services in which they will be inserted.

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